

An Electroencephalography Primer for Data Scientists

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Electroencephalography (EEG) is exceptionally important for medical diagnoses and research as well as neuroscience. The data generated and used in the process is highly complex and there is significant variability when it comes to its makeup.

This is to serve as a concise primer for data scientists explaining the basic concepts and highlighting the challenges and incongruencies within the field of EEG research.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: data science, electroencephalography, eeg, sampling

1 BACKGROUND

Electroencephalography

Electroencephalography (EEG) has been an important non-invasive tool for neuroscientific research[5] and medical diagnosis and is also of importance for monitoring in intensive care units[1][46].

While generally associated with epilepsy diagnosis and monitoring¹, its application in the diagnoses, predictions or monitoring of

- ADHD[2],
- autism[29],
- brain tumours[20],
- coma [19],
- dementia[4][40],
- depth of anaesthesia[9],
- mental illnesses[30],
- schizophrenia[8],
- traumatic brain injuries[31],

have been and are being researched. Furthermore it is being used in monitoring of alertness, brain development and cognitive engagement, as well as sleep physiology research[34][41].

Its basic principle is the measuring of voltage differences between electrodes induced by changes in membrane potential of firing cortical pyramidal neurons.

While EEG has been a field of research since 1929[42] it has steadily evolved and machine learning techniques, now to a certain extent the data scientist's domain, have been used in EEG research from at least 1988 onwards[11].

2 THE DATA

2.1 Attributes

EEG measurements are generally contained within a frequency range of 0.005 – 128 Hz. No consensus on their amplitude ranges exists. Taking the highest lower limit[12] and lowest upper limit [27] given, the resulting range would be 20 – 100 μ V.

EEG recordings are single- or multi-channel time-series of such measurements described in terms of *rhythm*, describing continuous, repetitive and uninterrupted activity and *transients*.

¹having become the standard procedure due to it enabling localization and classification of seizures[43] as well as reliability[9]

band	frequencies	amplitudes	typical amplitudes
delta	0.5-4 Hz	20 – 400 μ V	20 – 200 μ V
theta	4-8 Hz	5 – 100 μ V	disputed
alpha	8-13 Hz	5 – 100 μ V	20 – 50 μ V
beta	13-30 Hz	5 – 30 μ V	2 – 20 μ V
gamma	\geq 30 Hz	< 5 μ V	

Table 1. EEG rhythm categorization

The rhythmic components are thought of as divided into frequency-bands², each associated with certain regions of the scalp, mental states and pathologies therein[27] and may thus be the main focus of a research question or task.

See Table 1 for a summary based on [15], [18],[27], [34] and [44], assuming the widest ranges and most conservative typical ranges for the amplitudes whenever sources disagreed but were roughly compatible³.

While this segmentation has been criticized and alternatives to it have been proposed since at least the late 1970ies[17], it has remained the standard.

It is important to note that normality is dependent on the subject's age[3] and that there is significant individual variability[25]. Amplitude ranges in Table 1 refer to adults.

2.2 Artifacts

Given that the electrical activity generated is both miniscule to begin with and required to pass through the cerebrospinal fluid, meninges, the skull, and skin, which reduce the signal amplitude and spread it over a larger area, and that larger voltage potentials are generated by movements of the scalp, eyes, tongue or even heart, it is unsurprising that the signal-to-noise ratio is far from ideal[9].

This low signal-to-noise ratio and proclivity to interference (common to biosignals⁴ in general) leads to artifacts[12] which may cause false alarms⁵ or pose challenges to analysis and diagnostic methods. Artifacts can take a variety of forms and can be distinguished by their origin⁶, appearance⁷ and repeatability⁸.

²the gamma bandwidth is at times further subdivided into *low gamma* (25–70 Hz), *high gamma* (>70 Hz) and *ripples* (>100 Hz) [9], themselves divided into *ripples* (80 to 200Hz) and *fast ripples* (200 to 500Hz)[25]

³Most sources make no mention of a typical amplitude range for theta waves. Some[44] suggest > 20 μ V, while others[24] suggest it to be 8 – 10 μ V, showing large discrepancies between size and span. Normal theta activity, however, is considered largely poor or absent in primates[27], wherefore a lack of consensus on bounds is unsurprising

⁴Such as electrocardiography (ECG), electromyography (EMG), electroencephalography (EEG), etc.

⁵Lessening the quality of care by slowing staff response times and increasing noise pollution[10]

⁶*internal* sources, such as voluntary as well as involuntary body activities, or *external* ones, such as cable motion, electrode displacement or improper shielding

⁷*local* signifying appearance in only one recording channel or *global* signifying the appearance in multiple channels

⁸*irregular*, such as white noise or *periodic*, such as power line noise (50/60 cycle hum)

It is worth noting, that EEG rhythms are not equally affected by each artifact type, as for example gamma waves overlap entirely with the bandwidth of muscle activity[23], while alpha and lower frequency waves are not within its spectrum. Aliasing may, however, introduce high frequency errors into lower frequency bands.

2.3 Data Availability and Quality

In recent years there has been an increased interest in research of automatic artifact removal or correction⁹, often relying on machine-learning methods. A review of recent findings[33] can be used to demonstrate several key issues when it comes to reproducibility and comparisons of methods;

- (1) researchers generally work on different datasets
- (2) there was no information on dataset characteristics in roughly a third of the research reviewed
- (3) only a minority of datasets in general are being made publicly available
- (4) publicly available datasets generally are intended for specific purposes and are more often than not preprocessed
- (5) a variety of different metrics are being used to measure performance

While dataset sizes, balance and subjects will unavoidably and expectedly differ, there seems to be very little consistency with data gathering; factors neglected even in the above-mentioned review. Surprisingly, researchers have also noted that the sampling rate and recording process, both fundamental to the data quality, are often neglected or misinterpreted[45] and might be misrepresented in publications. Even publications describing their datasets do not always make reference to the sampling rate and recording setup[7].

3 DATA GATHERING

3.1 Sampling

Measurements of signals cannot be continuously taken, wherefore discrete approximation have to be relied on. The process of discretization of a continuous signal is called *sampling* and in the case of EEG, the data is being captured via electrodes, which themselves differ in materials and construction[41], though a discussion thereof is out of this paper's scope.

Ideally, uniquely and stably determined reconstructions from the discrete (digital) to the original continuous (analogue) signals should be possible, depending on the way the signals were sampled.

3.1.1 Aliasing.

The *aliasing effect*, roughly speaking a phenomenon causing different signal or signal components to become indistinguishable, can cause errors. Temporal frequency aliasing in one-dimensional sampling occurs when a signal is sampled too slowly, whereas spatial aliasing in higher dimensional applications is caused by sparse sampling in spaces with multidimensional sampling. While the term spatial aliasing is used to describe artifacts in imaging[36], spatial undersampling can be an issue in EEG. It is, however not referred to as spatial aliasing generally.

⁹The latter having to rely on training with simulated artifacts

3.1.2 Sampling Location and Number of Channels.

Given the localisation of brain activity and the need to compare voltage differences on at least two locations, the placement of electrodes is obviously crucial. Clarity of separation, the effects of overlapping and resulting demands for placement strategies are both out of scope and generally not a data scientists bailiwick, a basic awareness of the differences, however, is important when comparing datasets.

While the 19-electrode¹⁰ 10/20 systems¹¹ have been, though ambiguous[14], a quasi-standard, setups nowadays vary significantly. Higher density head-surface-based positioning setups as well as extensions of the 10/20 system to 10/10 and 10/5 systems¹² have been used. 128 and 256 channel setups have been commercially available for a decade and setups including up to 329 electrodes have been described and used [28].

While research suggests the necessity of 128 sensors across the head's full surface for adequate¹³ EEG sampling[39], fewer may be used for practical purposes;

An increase in electrode number is also an increase of cost, setup-time, cleaning effort¹⁴, memory requirements, processing power requirements and participant discomfort as well as potential for failure, artifacts, noise and calibration errors.

Moreover, a decrease of electrode numbers has been shown to lead to comparable results with proper pre-processing[37] or improve results for specific tasks[22] and there are several methods for inference of the sources' positions¹⁵[21].

A full sampling may itself not be desirable, if only certain brain areas are to be analysed. The American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM), for example, suggest using only a subset of the electrodes placed in the 10/20 system, with the others serving as backup and requires a minimum of three EEG derivations to to sample activity from the frontal, central and occipital regions[6].

3.1.3 Sampling Rate.

Most often measurements are taken equidistantly in time and their frequency is referred to as *sampling rate*, measured in Hz¹⁶.

While higher sampling rates naturally lead to higher similarity with the underlying signal, even within technologically feasible ranges the efficiency of computation, energy consumption¹⁷ and memory requirements are important issues.

As mentioned, an insufficient number of samples would not allow for the correct reconstruction or approximation of a signal (see Figure 1).

The appropriate number, however, highly depends on the signal being investigated;

¹⁰At times given as 21, counting the two electrodes used for contralateral referencing of all EEG electrodes, usually affixed to the earlobes

¹¹Named for the distances between adjacent electrodes being either 10% or 20% of the total front-back or right-left distance of the skull

¹²Which are "backwards compatible" with its standard positions

¹³Unaffected by spatial aliasing

¹⁴in the case of reusable electrodes

¹⁵also called the *inverse EEG problem*

¹⁶samples per second

¹⁷in the case of telemetry

Fig. 1. Demonstration of Temporal Aliasing as false assignment of a high frequency to a lower frequency part

According to the *Nyquist-Shannon*¹⁸ *sampling theorem* a band-limited signal can be exactly reconstructed through equidistant sampling if the sampling rate is at least twice as high as the signal's highest frequency[13]. Inversely, reconstructions above half the sampling rate are unreliable.

That may, however, not be enough, as alternating amplitudes of the oscillation add further complexity to the issue, and factors of 5 or 10 have been recommended[45].

There are several methods of temporal aliasing-prevention in EEG, the most popular being *filtering* prior to the sampling and *oversampling*, where a multiple of the number samples necessary to determine the function are measured, which eases requirements for anti-aliasing filters and increases the signal to noise ratio[16]. Signals are then most often resampled to a lower sample rate.

There appears to be no consensus as to sampling rates and technical limitations¹⁹ or other factors of consideration are not being mentioned.

Even for specific and similar tasks (such as EEG artifact recognition in the case of [32] and [38]) with data resampled to 200Hz the setups are considerably different; the former using a 32 electrode setup sampled at 1000 Hz without filtering and the latter using a 64 electrode setup sampled at 8192 Hz with a high pass filter at 1 Hz. Another approach[26] to the same task was done with a 192 electrode setup sampled at 25 kHz, downsampled to 5 kHz and pre-filtered at 2 kHz.

3.1.4 Filtering

Adding high- and low-pass filters²⁰ before recording is a common strategy to cut out unnecessary information and, in the case of the low-pass-filter, avoid aliasing. There is, however, no consensus on what to filter, as the desired filtering may be very task specific. While the AASM, for example, recommends a high-pass filter of 0.3 Hz and a low-pass filter of 35 Hz for the research of sleep

physiology[6], epilepsy researchers have noted that a low-pass filter of 35 Hz may filter out too much myogenic activity and make it look like epileptiform spikes, but they recommend a higher high-pass filter of 1 Hz[35], either being less concerned with the slowest activity or to remove the DC component and electrode drift associated with that frequency range[38], without actually justifying this choice.

It is also important to note that filtering prior to recording is therefore not equivalent to filtering of the recorded signal as for example an already introduced alias cannot be distinguished from the signal once sampling has occurred.

4 CONCLUSION

Data availability is, unfortunately, very limited and quality of the data's documentation is, unfortunately, comparatively low. This makes the collation of datasets unviable, as while resampling may allow for some limited alignment, it is only mechanical in nature; a captured signal's qualities cannot be aligned through it.

There appears to be almost no concern with reproducibility or comparability and little argumentation is put forward as to why choices in regard to data collection and transformation have been made, despite it being crucial.

The apparent lack of standardization in hardware furthermore makes a standardization of approaches both more difficult and far more unlikely.

5 OUTLOOK

It appears as though standardization of data gathering and pre-processing, even in subfields of study are tremendously unlikely in the near future, as no apparent efforts are being made and many a published paper does not explain, justify or even describe choices in the process of data gathering, signifying an attribution of low importance resulting in either omission, lack of consideration or both that may well be caused by single minded focus or limited awareness.

Both root causes could be addressed by data-scientists involved in such research.

As useful as standardization would be to reproducibility and comparability of results, it might not be reached before what are the most advanced systems possible become ubiquitous through increased accessibility and affordability, as currently researchers seem to rather focused on improving performance or predictive power.

Experimentation with different samplings of different subsets of electrodes on the same subject at the same time would be of great interest in order of being able to quantify the effects sampling regions, sampling rates and filtering have on the data gathered, as well as allowing for a meaningful comparison of downsampling strategies. Setup, however, would require a multitude of capturing devices and modified hardware, wherefore it seems an unlikely undertaking.

¹⁸ more accurately Kotelnikov-Nyquist-Whittaker-Shannon

¹⁹ such as the upper limit of recording

²⁰ Mathematically speaking, applying mappings that remove the low- or high-frequency components, respectively, done through convolution with a cardinal sine function

Studies of the effects of resampling and pre-processing on machine learning tasks may be of interest, although given the signal's determination by the original sampling rate²¹ and the specialized nature of their application would be unlikely to yield generalizable results.

EEG research's future and future trends themselves are not easily predicted, given its breadth of scope and depth of specificity. It seems, however, a somewhat safe bet that it will continue to grow in importance as a field.

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²¹and potential filtering

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